

GENOTYPIC AND PHENOTYPIC APPROACHES TO SELECT DURUM WHEAT ACCESSIONS ADAPTED TO CLIMATIC CHANGES AND ORGANIC AGRICULTURE

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Durum Wheat, Abiotic stress, GxE, SSR

Durum wheat (*Triticum turgidum* L. subsp. *durum* (Desf.) Husn.) adapted to drought stress and its consequences would ensure food security in most of the Mediterranean countries. In fact, abiotic stresses have a significant impact on durum wheat cultivation, with a registered loss of production up to 72% and 40% for drought and salinity, respectively. In addition, the demand of organic food, as well as healthy food, is increasing. However, there is still a lack of stable and high-yielding crop varieties specifically adapted for organic conditions and tolerant to abiotic stresses.

In order to characterize accession with different drought tolerance, genotypic and phenotypic approaches were used. Fifteen durum wheat accessions potentially suitable for organic agriculture were evaluated in field experiments over four successive seasons which were characterized by contrasting thermo-pluviometric values. The impact of the genotype–environment interaction (GxE) on productive and quality traits is an important parameter in selecting accession suitable for climatic changes. In addition, a genotypic diversity analysis of 38 microsatellites associated with traits important for organic farming and tolerance to abiotic stresses was performed.

GxE in conjunction with molecular analyses can improve durum wheat selection and breeding. We identified stable and high-yielding accessions with either high or stable-quality parameters. In addition, the used markers were identified as suitable for stable and high yield selection, as well as meeting quality parameters under organic farming conditions.

The present work was conducted in the frame of the ECOBREED project

(European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 771367).